

Project GRANT AGREEMENT N°101019427

D 5.2 – Website, Communication Kit and Social Media Presence

Executive Summary

The PALOMERA deliverable 5.2 *Website, Communication Kit and Social Media Presence* is an overview of the dedicated PALOMERA page under the OPERAS website umbrella, a guideline for the visual identity to be used in all communication/dissemination activities for the PALOMERA project and a summary of the planned social media presence via the project partners' channels. Its strategic aim is to support the communication/dissemination activities regarding the project results and the engagement with key stakeholder groups throughout the project, as well as the impact and future exploitation of the project's Key Exploitable Results (KERs). The document also includes the key facts and figures about the project that can be used as part of the messaging, and screenshots of the downloadable materials applicable in the communication/dissemination processes (within the Communication Kit available to the project partners via Google Drive). It has been developed as a complementary document to the Deliverable 5.1 *Dissemination, Outreach, Engagement, and Exploitation Plan* further referred to with the PEDR acronym in the document (<https://zenodo.org/record/7733579#.ZB1mNS8w17M>). The *Website, Communication Kit and Social Media Presence* document is subject to change as the project evolves. It will adapt to the project's needs and will be updated if necessary.

Keywords

Communication, Dissemination, social media, Website, PALOMERA

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Table of Acronyms

Acronyms	
ALLEA	European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities
AMU	Aix Marseille Université
CC 0	Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication
CC-BY	Creative Commons Attribution International Public License
CoNOSC	Council for National Open Science Coordination
DACH	Deutschland (Germany), Austria, Confœderatio Helvetica (Switzerland)
DARIAH	The Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
EC	European Commission
ED&I	Equity, Diversity & Inclusivity
ERA	European Research Area
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESF	European Science Foundation
EU	European Union
EUA	European University Association
IBL PAN	Instytut Badań Literackich Polskiej Akademii Nauk
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LIBER	Ligue des Bibliothèques Européennes de Recherche – Association of European Research Libraries
M#	Month
OA	Open Access
OABN	Open Access Book Network
OASPA	Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association
OATP	Open Access Tracking Project
OBP	Open Book Publishers
OE	OpenEdition
OER	Open Educational Resource
OPERAS	Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities
PEDR	Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (while in this document it will be referred to as Dissemination, Outreach, Engagement, and Exploitation Plan)
PALOMERA	Policy Alignment of Open Access Monographs in the European Research Area
RFO	Research Funding Organizations
RPO	Research Performing Organizations
SIG	Special Interest Group
SO	Specific Objective
UGOE	Georg August Universität Göttingen
UN	United Nations
UC	University of Coimbra
UNIBI	University of Bielefeld
WP#	Work Package
ZRC SAZU	The Research Center of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts

1 Introduction

The deliverable 5.2 *Website, Communication Kit and Social Media Presence* document presents:

- The PALOMERA key facts & figures relevant to the community and that can be used in the messaging activities;
- The details about the PALOMERA page included on the OPERAS website;
- The guideline for the visual identity to be used in all communication/dissemination activities for the PALOMERA project;
- A summary of the planned social media presence via the project partners' channels plus how to use those channels;
- The Communication Kit available to the project partners via a Google Drive folder including the project's visual identity with the materials such as logo files, document templates, website banners and similar.

The research infrastructure OPERAS with the tagline “open scholarly communication in the European research area for social sciences and humanities” will ensure long-term sustainability of PALOMERA's information, its results and visibility. PALOMERA will benefit from the OPERAS community due to the support and infrastructure it has developed for the Open Access book community, as well as stakeholder overlaps among the various projects OPERAS is part of or coordinates. The Open Access Books Network (OABN), as an OPERAS special interest group (SIG), will be instrumental in communicating and engaging with the Open Access book community relevant to PALOMERA. For those reasons, a decision has been made to not create a separate PALOMERA website but to include a PALOMERA project page (<https://operas-eu.org/projects/palomera/>) under the OPERAS website umbrella, alongside the other projects coordinated by OPERAS previously or currently running. This will make PALOMERA more discoverable to key stakeholders than if it had an independent website.

The materials in the Communication Kit are:

- Partially modifiable; some can be adapted for the communication or dissemination needs and the channel (different social media posts, flyers and PowerPoint presentation templates);
- Provided under an open licence (usually Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC-BY)).

The Communication Kit is expected to include other items as the project evolves, taking into account emerging needs. Part of it (such as the logo, banner, social media templates, generic PowerPoint presentation template and flyer template) has been prepared by Laetitia MARTIN, an artist affiliated to "Maison des Artistes", while the rest was created by the Work Package (WP) 5 partners. The Communication Kit accompanies the PEDR that defines the stakeholders, how to address them and the communication/dissemination measures.

The below list includes the key facts and figures that can be used when communicating about the PALOMERA project using various channels and methods.

Acronym	PALOMERA – Policy Alignment of Open access Monographs in the European Research Area
Project start date & launch	1 January 2023
Project end date	31 December 2024
Kick-off meeting	17–18 January 2023
Project duration	24 months
Funding	Funded under Horizon Europe: Reforming and enhancing the European R&I System (https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101094270).
Call framework	HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01
Partners	<p>16 in total:</p> <p>AMU (OE) </p>
Coordinating partner	OPERAS
Geographical scope	European research area (ERA)
Work packages	<p>WP1 Coordination and management</p> <p>WP2 Building the Knowledge Base</p> <p>WP3 Analysing the Knowledge Base</p> <p>WP4 Recommendations and resources</p> <p>WP5 Communication, dissemination, engagement and validation</p>

Key objectives	<p>The PALOMERA general objective to speed up the transition to Open Access for books is divided into five specific objectives (SOs):</p> <p>(SO1) To develop and coordinate a knowledge base with qualitative and quantitative data on the Open Access book policy landscape in Europe.</p> <p>(SO2) To understand the challenges preventing research funding organisations (RFOs) and research performing organisations (RPOs) from developing and aligning on policies for Open Access books, including challenges concerning current incentive structures and research assessment proxies.</p> <p>(SO3) To engage relevant stakeholders in the Open Access books community in the validation of the collected data and the analyses hereof, and the evidence-based, actionable recommendations on how to further advance alignment, diversity, equity, and inclusion in Open Access book policies and strategies.</p> <p>(SO4) To help RFOs and RPOs develop policies and strategies that will advance the transition to Open Access books through the establishment and operation of a trusted forum for RPOs and RFOs on Open Access books (hereafter referred to as the Funder Forum).</p> <p>(SO5) To learn from and share experiences with RFOs outside of the ERA who have developed Open Access book policies.</p>
Project expected results	<p>A Knowledge Base comprising relevant information on Open Access book publishing landscape and policies</p> <p>A report identifying the bottlenecks that prevent the adoption of Open Access book policies and strategies</p> <p>A set of actionable and evidence-based recommendations to the adoption of Open Access book policies and strategies</p> <p>A service helping RFOs align their policy development (the Funder Forum)</p> <p>Two policy briefs summarising key findings and results in plain text targeted at the most senior level of RFOs and RPOs</p> <p>Research data (from policy-analysis, surveys, interviews, workshops and similar)</p> <p>Scientific publications (individual and joint publications relating to the project)</p>
Key stakeholders target groups	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. National open science policy makers 2. RFOs 3. RPOs 4. Publishers 5. Infrastructure providers 6. Libraries 7. Researchers 8. Scholarly societies

Advisory Board members	Science Europe Secretary General, Lidia Borrell-Damián European University Association (EUA) Secretary General, Amanda Crowfoot All European Academies (ALLEA) Executive Director, Matthias Johannsen Open Access Australasia Executive Committee Member, Danny Kingsley Adam Mickiewicz University Prof., dr. Emanuel Kulczycki Directorate of Scientific Research Ministry of the Wallonia-Brussels Federation Director General, Marc Vanholsbeeck Central European University Press Executive Chair, Frances Pinter
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Table 1 PALOMERA Key facts and figures

2 Website

The PALOMERA page <https://operas-eu.org/projects/palomera/> (part of the OPERAS website <https://operas-eu.org/>) contains an outline of the motivation for the project, the ways PALOMERA will investigate the identified issues, and the target audiences for the recommendations and deliverables that will arise from the work. Practical information is also included, such as the timeframe for the project, a list of the members and partners within the consortia and links out to European Commission information, such as openly available grant details, programme and the amount of funding to be allocated across organisations.

Figure 1 OPERAS website

3 Communication Kit

The Communication Kit includes communication and dissemination tools and templates to be used by the PALOMERA project partners. All related materials are shared with project consortium members via the project's Google Drive folder.

The materials will be available under the CC-BY license and, where possible, the PALOMERA project partners are encouraged to translate them into local languages for more effective communication and dissemination activities. The materials can also be reused and localised as Open Education Resources (OER).

3.1 Visual Identity

The PALOMERA project has a dedicated visual identity that has been developed early in the project so it can support all the communication as well as dissemination activities. The next sections contain an overview of all the visual identity elements.

3.2 Logo

PALOMERA's logo has been approved by the project coordinator. In particular, the following items have been prepared and shared with project partners:

- Logo;
- Favicon.

The PALOMERA logo consists of a symbol and the wordmark "PALOMERA" which are used as a unit. The symbol is in the shape of book pages symbolising the figure "monograph" implied in the acronym. There are two approved variations of the logo, one with and the other without a circle. The project logo has been developed for use in colour or negative, alongside the European Union (EU) emblem on all project materials.

Figure 2 PALOMERA logos

3.3 Font

The dedicated font for the PALOMERA project is Playfair Display (<https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Playfair+Display>) and will be used where possible both internally and externally. An example of this font can be seen below. The full instructions on how to install and download this font are part of the dedicated Communication Kit folder on Google Drive.

Figure 3 PALOMERA font

3.4 Colour Code

The PALOMERA logo's colour code, seen below, can also be used for other text where applicable.

Figure 4 PALOMERA colour code

3.5 Watermark

The Communication Kit includes a watermark that can be used across documents in Word, PDF, PowerPoint, posters and similar.

Figure 5 PALOMERA watermark

3.6 Banners

The PALOMERA banners have been created for websites, email signatures and social media channels' needs, but can also be used in other communication and promotional materials.

Figure 6 PALOMERA banners

3.7 Flyer template

For the purpose of creating a diverse spectrum of posts and materials, a flyer template has been created with the option for further modification by the partners when they wish to adapt it to their needs (in cases where they are promoting project results, events, or other announcement and to give them space to add their own logo alongside the PALOMERA and EU logos). The flyer will be available in 3 file formats for modification in PowerPoint, Photoshop and InDesign. The flyer is coloured, one-sided and A5 size.

Figure 7 PALOMERA flyer

3.8 PowerPoint presentation templates

The Communication Kit includes 2 sets of PowerPoint slide decks where the initial design has been provided for purposes such as WP meetings, presentations and similar. A variation has been created internally by the partners for use at conferences, webinars, workshops and similar.

Figure 8 PALOMERA PowerPoint slide deck – generic template

Figure 9 About PALOMERA PowerPoint slide deck

3.9 Word document template

A word document template has been created for both internal and external purposes.

Figure 10 PALOMERA Word template

3.10 Visibility of EU funding

In accordance with the obligations regarding the dissemination of results, as stated in the Grant Agreement, all project materials produced in the context of the project (publications, website, flyer etc.) must acknowledge EU funding and should be accompanied by the EU emblem.

Where necessary, the following text should be included:

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

There are a few variations of the emblem as per the below screenshots.

Figure 11 EU Emblems

3.11 Language-Related aspects of communication

When spreading information about the PALOMERA project via the website or social media channels and when producing communication materials, we pay attention to some general language-related aspects listed below.

- Preference for British English spelling over the spelling norms of other varieties of English;
- Using local languages in the communication where possible for a more effective reach to target stakeholders;

- Use of gender-sensitive language, i.e. use non-discriminatory language, make gender visible when it is relevant for communication and not visible when it is irrelevant (useful guidelines are the “Toolkit on Gender-sensitive Communication” by the European Institute for Gender Equality¹ and the United Nations (UN) guidelines for gender-inclusive language in English²);
- Tailoring the communication (wording, style, complexity) to the respective audience.

When communicating with a wider, non-specialist target audience, it is recommended to ensure accessibility by keeping the message short and simple. This can be done by adhering to the following principles:

- Use mainstream language and avoid jargon and technical terms;
- Use as few acronyms as possible;
- If acronyms are used, they need to be spelled out and explained;
- Explain what the terminology means in the context of the project and future service.

3.12 Partner newsletters and blogs

Similarly, to the social media channels, a decision has been made to not create a PALOMERA specific newsletter but to include news regarding the project and its activities as well as results in project partners’ blogs or newsletters. The below table shows an overview of some of the newsletters available for this effort. There will be others added as the project develops and the communication/dissemination spreads to the larger community.

Partner newsletter	Frequency	Links
UniNews (UGOE)	Weekly	http://newsletter.uni-goettingen.de/
DARIAH ERIC Newsletter	Monthly	https://www.dariah.eu/dariah-newsletters-archive/
OPERAS-PL - IBL PAN	Monthly	https://operas.pl/o-nas/
LIBER insider (LIBER)	Monthly	https://libereurope.eu/liber-insider/
SPARC Europe Newsletter	Monthly	https://sparceurope.org/newsletter-archive/
OpenEdition (AMU)	Monthly	https://www.openedition.org/41045
OAPEN	Bimonthly	https://us4.campaign-archive.com/home/?u=314fa411ba5eaace7244c95e1&id=e31e6f80e1
OBP Newsletter	Quarterly	https://blogs.openbookpublishers.com/tag/obp-newsletter/
OPERAS	Quarterly	https://operas-eu.org/operas-newsletter/ https://operas-eu.org/operas-newsletter-archive/
Jisc	Quarterly	https://www.jisc.ac.uk/forms/sign-up-for-our-open-research-digest

Table 2 Partners’ newsletters

¹ European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE) (2019). Toolkit on Gender-sensitive Communication. A resource for policymakers, legislators, media and anyone else with an interest in making their communication more inclusive. <https://eige.europa.eu/publications/toolkit-gender-sensitive-communication>

² <https://www.un.org/en/gender-inclusive-language/guidelines.shtml>

Partner blogs	Links
DARIAH Open	https://dariahopen.hypotheses.org/
IBL PAN / OPERAS-PL blog	https://otwartanauka.hypotheses.org/
JISC Research	https://research.jiscinvolve.org/wp/
OAPEN	https://oapen.hypotheses.org/
OASPA Blog	https://oaspa.org/blog/
Open Book Publishers Blog	https://blogs.openbookpublishers.com
OpenEdition (AMU)	https://oep.hypotheses.org (EN) https://leo.hypotheses.org/ (FR)
OPERAS-PL	https://operas.pl/
OPERAS Blog	https://operas.hypotheses.org/
OABN	https://openaccessbooksnetwork.hcommons.org/blog/
SPARC Europe Blogs	https://sparceurope.org/news/ https://sparceurope.org/news/
UC Open Science	https://www.uc.pt/en/openscience/
BLUG - UGOE	https://www.blog.uni-goettingen.de/en/mainpage/
Universität Bielefeld Blog	https://blog.ub.uni-bielefeld.de/

Table 3 Partners' blogs

3.13 Mailing Lists

Partners will be encouraged to use the mailing lists to which they are subscribed to promote the project as soon as updates about the project arise. To disseminate our work through these channels, PALOMERA will approach these mailing lists with key project news stories. Below are the examples of some of the mailing lists:

- [Coimbra University Press](#) (UC)
- [GOAL](#) (OASPA)
- [InetBib](#) (UGOE)
- [IP-OA Forum](#) (UGOE)
- [Interdisciplinary Research Institute](#) (UC)
- [Liblicense](#) (OASPA)
- LIS-E-RESOURCES@JISCMAIL.AC.UK (JISC)
- UNIVERSITYPRESS@JISCMAIL.AC.UK (JISC)
- OAGOODPRACTICE@JISCMAIL.AC.UK (JISC)
- OPERAS Members

3.14 Monitoring of activities for reporting purposes

To be able to gather the development, deployment and impact of the communication and dissemination activities, an Excel File Tracker has been developed and made available to the partners in the PALOMERA Google Drive folder. Each partner shall add the details of the communication and dissemination activities they are performing, the events they are organizing or hosting and the publications they are sharing with the community. The Tracker also includes a tab to monitor the key performance indicators (KPIs) that will be used for the continuous reporting to the European Commission.

Nº	Channel used	Communication Activity	Objective / expected impact (Why?)	Link to WP	Description of Implemented activity	Target audience (who?)
1	Twitter	Amplifying PALOMERA social me	Reach a wider audience. We h		5 - Sharing news of the PALOMERA / O	
2	Twitter	Amplifying PALOMERA social me	Reach a wider audience. We h		5 - Sharing news of the PALOMERA / O	
3	Twitter	Amplifying PALOMERA social me	Promote to schol comms com		5 - Sharing news of the PALOMERA / O	
4	Twitter	Amplifying PALOMERA social me			5 - Sharing news of the PALOMERA / O	
5	LinkedIn	Introducing the LinkedIn Group t	Reach a wider audience and tl		5 - Sharing PALOMERA key facts and fig	All stakeholders
6	Twitter	Amplifying PALOMERA social me	Promote to schol comms com		5 - Sharing news of the PALOMERA / O	All stakeholders
7	LinkedIn	Amplifying PALOMERA social me	Promote to schol comms com		5 - Sharing news of the PALOMERA / O	All stakeholders
8	LinkedIn	Amplifying PALOMERA social me	Promote to schol comms com		5 - Sharing news of the PALOMERA / O	All stakeholders
9	Twitter	Promoting OABN/PALOMERA ewi	Reach a wide range of the OAI		5 - Sharing news of the PALOMERA / O	All stakeholders
10	Twitter	Promoting OABN/PALOMERA ewi	Reach a wide range of the OAI		5 - Sharing news of the PALOMERA / O	All stakeholders
11	Mastodon	Promoting OABN/PALOMERA ewi	Reach a wide range of the OAI		5 - Sharing news of the PALOMERA / O	All stakeholders
12	Mastodon	Promoting OABN/PALOMERA ewi	Reach a wide range of the OAI		5 - Sharing news of the PALOMERA / O	All stakeholders
13	OABN Blog	Announcing OABN/PALOMERA S	Reach a wide range of the OAI		5 - Sharing news of the PALOMERA / O	All stakeholders
14	OABN Mailing List	Announcing OABN/PALOMERA S	Reach a wide range of the OAI		5 - Sharing news of the PALOMERA / O	All stakeholders
15	DARIAH website	Announcing kick off for PALOMEI	Inform the DARIAH communit		5 - Sharing news of the PALOMERA / OABN collaboration	
16				Choose option		
17				Choose option		
18				Choose option		
19				Choose option		
20				Choose option		

Figure 12 PALOMERA communication, dissemination and engagement activities

3.15 OATP Tagging

To increase the visibility and reach of the PALOMERA communications and dissemination activities, it is suggested that the project partners adopt the Open Access Tracking Project (OATP) tagging practice. This is a social tagging project to capture and communicate news on open science. “It has two missions: create real-time alerts for OA-related developments, and organize knowledge of the field, by tag or subtopic, for easy searching and sharing.”³ Each partner can sign up to be a voluntary tagger for PALOMERA relevant news within OATP. To do this, they can follow the instructions here: https://cyber.harvard.edu/hoap/OATP_FAQ.

4 Social Media Presence

4.1 Social Media post templates

After a consultation among the PALOMERA project partners, a decision has been made not to create specific PALOMERA social media channels since all the partners have well-established channels that will allow for a more effective and immediate reach to the right audience, together with the OABN social media channels. This aligns with what was outlined in the grant proposal and PEDR mentioning that the main activities will run via OPERAS and OABN communication channels.

The PALOMERA social media post templates have two variations to accommodate the needs of different social media channels used by the project partners – Facebook, Twitter, Instagram and LinkedIn. They will be available in three file formats for modification in PowerPoint, Photoshop and InDesign.

³ https://cyber.harvard.edu/hoap/OATP_introduction

Figure 13 PALOMERA social media templates

4.2 Hashtags and channels

In order to create a unified way of finding information about the PALOMERA project across various social media channels, project partners have agreed to use pre-selected hashtags when creating posts for the project. The selection is listed below. Project partners are welcome to add additional hashtags within the posts they are sharing, however it is advisable to limit the number of hashtags to a maximum of five per post. The hashtags selected should always include #PALOMERA.

#PALOMERA
 #OAbooks
 #OApolicy
 #OpenAccess
 #OpenScience

The channels that will be used for the communication and dissemination purposes will be the various social media channels of the project partners, including but not limited to the below table listing some of the channels.

Channel	Partners	Links
Facebook	IBL PAN	https://www.facebook.com/InstytutBadanLiterackichPAN , https://www.facebook.com/Centrum.Humanistyki.Cyfrowej
	LIBER	https://www.facebook.com/LIBEREurope/
	OPERAS	https://www.facebook.com/OPERASEU/
	UC	https://www.facebook.com/univdecoimbra https://www.facebook.com/UCOpenScience
	UGOE	https://de-de.facebook.com/SUB.INFO/
	UNIBI	https://www.facebook.com/BielefeldUniversity
	ZRC SAZU	https://www.facebook.com/ZRC-SAZU-187909304594445
Instagram	IBL PAN	https://www.instagram.com/instytut_badan_literackich_pan/
	OPERAS	https://www.instagram.com/operaseu/
	UC	https://www.instagram.com/ucopenscience/ https://www.instagram.com/ucoimbra/
	UGOE	https://www.instagram.com/unigoettingen/?hl=de
	UNIBI	https://www.instagram.com/bielefelduniversity/
	ZRC SAZU	https://www.instagram.com/zrcsazu/
LinkedIn	DARIAH ERIC	https://www.linkedin.com/company/dariah-eric/

Channel	Partners	Links
	HANKEN	https://www.linkedin.com/school/hanken-svenska-handelshogskolan
	IBL PAN	https://pl.linkedin.com/company/ibl-pan
	JISC	https://www.linkedin.com/company/jisc/
	LIBER	https://www.linkedin.com/company/libereurope/
	OASPA	https://nl.linkedin.com/company/oaspa
	OPERAS	https://www.linkedin.com/company/operas/
	SPARC EUROPE	https://www.linkedin.com/company/sparc-europe
	UC	https://pt.linkedin.com/school/universidade-de-coimbra/
Mastodon	OBP	https://hcommons.social/@OpenBookPublish
	UGOE	https://openbiblio.social/@subugoe
TikTok	UC	https://www.tiktok.com/@ucoimbra
Twitter	cOAlition S	https://twitter.com/cOAlitionS_OA
	DARIAH ERIC	https://twitter.com/DARIAHeu
	HANKEN	https://twitter.com/Hanken_fi
	IBL PAN	https://twitter.com/IBLPAN
	JISC	https://twitter.com/JiscOpenRes https://twitter.com/Jisc
	LIBER	https://twitter.com/LIBEReurope
	OABN	https://twitter.com/oabooksnetwork
	OAPEN	https://twitter.com/OAPENbooks https://twitter.com/DOABooks
	OASPA	https://twitter.com/OASPA
	OBP	https://twitter.com/OpenBookPublish
	OpenEdition (AMU)	https://twitter.com/OpenEditionPro https://twitter.com/OpenEditionNews
	OPERAS	https://twitter.com/OPERASEU/
	SPARC Europe	https://twitter.com/SPARC_EU
	UC	https://twitter.com/uc_openscience https://twitter.com/UnivdeCoimbra
	UGOE	https://twitter.com/subugoe
	UNIBI	https://twitter.com/ub_bi
	ZRC SAZU	https://twitter.com/ZrcSazu
YouTube	cOAlition S	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCD1fwyXxW1P4z_Spfkr7lAg
	DARIAH ERIC	https://www.youtube.com/@DariahEurope
	HANKEN	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCD9YbKeZrQOUIPI-yRTj-kQ
	IBL PAN	https://www.youtube.com/@instytutbadanliterackichpa3271
	JISC	https://www.youtube.com/user/JISCmedia
	LIBER	https://www.youtube.com/@libervideo
	OAPEN	https://www.youtube.com/@oapenfoundation1245
	OASPA	https://www.youtube.com/@OASPA
	OBP	https://www.youtube.com/@openbookpublishers/
	OPERAS	https://www.youtube.com/@operas-eu/featured
	OABN	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCqaYuVBBGe3XihJ7wHtY1ZA
	UC	https://www.youtube.com/@UnivDeCoimbra
	UGOE	https://www.youtube.com/@UnigoettingenDeVideos

Channel	Partners	Links
	UNIBI	https://www.youtube.com/@BielefeldUniversity
	ZRC SAZU	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCVbNfSD_r7m8cbmxq5bm_v2w/featured

Table 4 Partners' social media channels

The different social media channels were chosen to address our different stakeholder groups, as defined in detail in the PEDR, and different communities in the diverse European research landscape.

Figure 14 PALOMERA stakeholders

Social media channels allow us to reach a broader audience than through more traditional dissemination activities. All social media accounts are administered and maintained by the partner owning the relevant channel.

The goals we want to reach with the social media channels are:

- Increase the visibility and public awareness of the project;
- Promote our project and the associated brand, results and outputs;
- Promote the events and activities of the project and of the consortium partners;
- Promote the European Commission as our funding institution.

The focus of our social media communication activities is primarily on the project partners' Twitter channels since this is where important discussions in the field of Open Science and research infrastructures are taking place, however early in the project we will explore which channels work best for each stakeholder group by using the monitoring tracker described in 3.14, and posts will occasionally be made also on Facebook, LinkedIn and Instagram.

To develop our storytelling in the different channels, it is recommended to:

- Use a picture with elements from the PALOMERA visual identity design available to project partners via the shared Google Drive folder and/or images representing the content (using CC0-licensed [Creative Commons Zero] images and icons from a licenced library);
- Tag involved persons, institutions and partners;
- Use hashtags of events or topics that relate to our fields of activity (a maximum of 5 per post);
- Add links to relevant websites (e.g. events websites, posts on the OPERAS blog or partners' blogs and websites);
- Consider accessibility needs, in particular including [alt text](#) for any images and minimise the use of emojis.

In order to encourage all partners of the PALOMERA consortium to take an active part in the conversations about the project, and to spread our news as widely as possible, also within the national communities, partners are encouraged to:

- Follow each other on all social media channels;
- Repost relevant PALOMERA social media posts as often as possible (including the ones written in other languages) and adding value with own comments;
- Post PALOMERA-related messages with a comment in their national language via their own social media accounts and using chosen PALOMERA hashtags;
- Inform the WP5 lead (OPERAS) about any news they would like to see posted from the OPERAS accounts directly;
- Post about PALOMERA events and other communication when requested by the WP5 lead (OPERAS).

The main topics to communicate via social media channels are:

- Introduce the PALOMERA partners and team members during the first months of the project;
- Share publications/research results;
- Promote hosted and organized public events;
- Produce live coverage of events attended by PALOMERA team members (e.g. live-tweeting a presentation);
- Share news about PALOMERA blog posts;
- Re-post social media posts showcasing content related to PALOMERA and its activities (results, events, partners etc.) with comments to add value.

For the purpose of making sure the communications professionals across the partners are aware of events and news to share from the respective partners, we have developed an internal PALOMERA communications mailing list that will be used to inform them of such activities in advance.

5 Conclusion

The PALOMERA deliverable 5.2 *Website, Communication Kit and Social Media Presence* document with its sections represents the PALOMERA project's visual identity, Communication Kit, website and social media presence. This will guide all the project partners in the communication and dissemination activities directed towards the relevant communities. It's crucial in supporting the impact of the project and goes hand in hand with the PEDR document developed separately. All the project partners part of the WP5 and beyond have collaborated in creating this document and will contribute to its future updates as well.

